

Public Trust as Influenced by School Fiscal Transparency

Jearlyn B. Dijon

Abstract. The study unfolded to determine the public trust as influenced by school fiscal transparency in Governor Generoso District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. The study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data collected were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r , and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that fiscal transparency shows financial reporting is often manifested. Accountability for resource allocation, public participation in budgeting, financial audits, and access to financial information was sometimes manifested, while communication and feedback and consistent classroom management were sometimes manifested, while parent and community engagement, accountability for results, and responsive conflict resolution were often manifested; consistent and fair policy and transparency were sometimes manifested. There was a significant correlation between fiscal transparency and public trust. All domains of budgetary openness regarding access to financial information, financial reporting, public participation in budgeting, financial audits, and accountability for resource allocation suggest significant influence over public trust. Future research may explore the effectiveness of different communication strategies for financial information and assess the role of community engagement in building trust.

KEY WORDS

1. parents' involvement
2. drug education program
3. fiscal transparency
4. accountability for resource allocation

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1. Introduction

Fiscal transparency is pivotal in ensuring accountability and trust within the school community. It allows stakeholders to understand how financial resources are allocated, whether funds are spent efficiently, and whether the school is fulfilling its educational mission. When fiscal transparency is robust, it can lead to improved decision-making, stakeholder engagement, and, ultimately, better academic outcomes. Achieving fiscal transparency in school operations and management can be challenging despite its importance. Poynton et al. (2018) said that school

finances could be intricate, with multiple funding sources, such as government allocations, grants, and parent contributions. This complexity can make it challenging to present financial information clearly and understandably. Many schools need more resources, including limited personnel and technological infrastructure, making establishing robust financial reporting systems challenging. School administrators and staff may need more financial management and reporting training, hindering their ability to communicate financial information effectively.

Some educational institutions may resist transparency due to concerns about disclosing financial vulnerabilities, potentially leading to negative perceptions among stakeholders. Evolving financial regulations and reporting requirements can further complicate efforts to maintain consistent fiscal transparency practices. To address these challenges and improve fiscal transparency in school operations and management. Invest in training and professional development for school administrators and staff to enhance financial literacy and reporting skills. Implement user-friendly financial management software and reporting tools to streamline financial processes and improve accessibility. Actively involve parents, teachers, students, and the local community in budgeting, decision-making, and financial planning, fostering a culture of transparency and accountability. Conduct independent financial audits to ensure compliance with regulations and maintain financial integrity. Communicate financial information clearly and comprehensively to stakeholders, utilizing plain language and visual aids where possible (Smith Xu, 2023). In the Philippines, Public trust in education is paramount as it underpins the relationship between educational institutions and the communities they serve. When trust is high, parents are more likely to be engaged in their children's education, students are motivated to learn, and teachers are encouraged

to excel in their roles. Trust is essential for successfully implementing education policies and reforms (Molina Lamb, 2022). Concerns persisted about the quality of education in the Philippines, including issues related to outdated curricula, teacher shortages, and limited access to quality resources. Uneven distribution of resources, particularly in rural areas, led to disparities in educational facilities and opportunities. Reports of corruption within the education system, including allegations of misappropriation of funds, eroded trust among stakeholders. The intersection of politics and education continued to be a contentious issue, with appointments of education officials sometimes influenced by political considerations rather than merit. (Vikarman, et.al., 2021) The Philippine government introduced various education reforms, such as the K to 12 program, aimed at improving the quality of education and aligning it with international standards. Transparency and accountability measures, including financial audits and investigations, were implemented to address corruption and mismanagement. Investments were made in infrastructure development to address disparities in school facilities and resources. Efforts were made to engage parents and communities in the educational process, fostering a sense of ownership and collaboration (Raczynski et al., 2022).

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the processes and steps for conducting the study. These include selecting the study's design, the respondents and sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, the ethical considerations, and the data analysis. These steps were essential to ensure appropriateness and correctness and produce sound data collection, analysis, and interpretation.

2.1. Research Design—The study used the non-experimental, descriptive-correlational research design, which investigates the degree to which two or more variables are related. It

does not involve manipulating variables but rather measures and analyses their existing relationship (Creswell, 2014). This study's correlational research design can examine the re-

relationship between the extent of School Heads' role in authentic leadership and Teachers' organizational commitment. According to Creswell (2014), a descriptive-correlational research design describes and explains the relationship between two or more variables. The main goal of this type of research design was to identify the relationship between variables, and it can be used to make predictions about future events. Descriptive-correlational research designs were used to describe the relationships between variables. Researchers collect data on two or more variables and then analyze the data to determine if there is a relationship between them. This type of research was used to generate hypotheses for future studies (Campbell Stanley, 1963). Finally, a descriptive-correlational research design could be valuable when experimental manipulation of variables is not possible or ethical. For example, manipulating variables such as age, gender, or medical condition to examine their effects on other variables may be unethical. In such cases, a descriptive-correlational design can provide a valuable alternative for investigating the relationships between variables of interest without requiring manipulation or control of those variables. In this study, the relationship between fiscal transparency and public trust among schools in the Gov. Generoso District is assumed to exist; thus, the research design's measure was appropriate for this study.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—Respondents of the study were the Elementary School Teachers of Governor Generoso District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. She used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where 120 respondents were taken randomly from each School in the Governor Generoso District's Elementary Schools. Once randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platforms and face-to-face, considering the availability of Wi-Fi connections; they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional de-

velopment status. These teacher-respondents were the teachers who were actively and directly involved in most of the school's operations and governance activities. Management of the School's MOOE and other sources of local funds is available during procurement and utilization of funds to support programs, projects, and activities in line with the implementation plan directed by DepED mandates under the MATATAG Agenda. Moreover, teachers with skills in strategizing the simplification of operational processes and management in school apart from curriculum implementation and delivery are likewise trying to improve the system to achieve performance given the financial management system. They are qualified for the role and are expected to have performed and contributed to the betterment of the schools and the stakeholders' participation, given the new regular learning system during SY 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various seminars and trainings in the school management and curriculum development delivery system.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This research study used the adapted instrument from reviewed literature and related studies. The researcher took time gathering and reading reviews of related literature to develop concepts for the content that support the instrument and its corresponding strands in articulating the set of question items, reducing threats to validity. As the authors argued, items were adapted from the reviewed literature. The survey questionnaire had two parts, one determined the extent of fiscal transparency regarding access to financial information, financial reporting, public participation in budgeting, financial audits, and accountability for resource allocation. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the extent of public trust regarding transparency, accountability for results, parent and community engagement, responsiveness to conflict resolution, and consistent and fair policy. Further, the

survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 confidence level. They generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.879, which means 87.9 percent confidence in the validity and reliability of the survey statement’s constructs (Pallant, 2010). The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of schools’ fiscal transparency; the scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation are provided below:

Scale and Descriptive Rating for Schools’ Fiscal Transparency

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The schools’ fiscal transparency is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The schools’ fiscal transparency is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The schools’ fiscal transparency is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The schools’ fiscal transparency is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The schools’ fiscal transparency is not manifested

Scale and Descriptive Rating for School’s Public Trust

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The school’s public trust is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The school’s public trust is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The school’s public trust is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The school’s public trust is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The school’s public trust is not manifested

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The data-gathering procedure within a research project involves a series of critical steps, and among them is the ethical process of obtaining permission to conduct the study. This step was integral to upholding core principles of respect, transparency, and responsible research conduct. The statements are based on the policies and guidelines of the college where the researcher is studying; as part of the request, researchers articulate their intentions for data collection, analysis, and dissemination, illustrating how these align with the overall research goals. This correspondence should address any concerns or questions anticipated from recipients, alongside assurances regarding ethical safeguards, confidentiality measures, and the study’s potential benefits. The formal permission request was then made, explicitly seeking authorization to pro-

ceed and emphasizing the significance of their support for the research’s success. Permission to conduct the study. On October 2023, before collecting data, the researcher must obtain permission from the appropriate authorities, such as the research adviser, the Dean of the Rizal Memorial Colleges, and the top management of DepEd Davao Oriental Division through the channel. This permission-seeking process typically involves submitting a research proposal with information about the study design, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. The researcher provided information about the purpose and goals of the study and how the data were collected, analyzed, and reported. In addition, in January 2024, the researcher ensured that all participants were fully informed about the study and their rights and that they provided informed consent before participating. Distri-

bution and retrieval of the questionnaire. In the first week of April 2024, the researcher ensured the accuracy and completeness of data, and the distribution and retrieval of questionnaires were conducted in a standardized and systematic manner. She went into considering the following conditions: The researcher identified the appropriate study target population and ensured the questionnaire was distributed only to individuals who met the inclusion criteria. The researcher obtained informed consent from all participants before distributing the questionnaire. This may involve providing information about the purpose and goals of the study, as well as any potential risks and benefits. She ensured the questionnaire was anonymous, meaning respondents were not identified by name or other personal information. The researcher also ensured that the data collected was confidential and only used for the study. The researcher standardized the process for distributing the questionnaire to ensure that all participants received the exact instructions and had the same opportunity to complete it. Participants were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire and were allowed to ask any questions they may have about the process. She then collected the completed questionnaires in a timely and organized manner to ensure that data was recovered and found. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The following are the general conditions

that should be followed for the collation and statistical treatment of data as part of the data-gathering procedure: The data were accurate and free from errors. This means they should be checked and validated to ensure their correctness. The data were complete, meaning all necessary information had been collected. This is important because incomplete data can lead to incorrect conclusions. She made it consistent, that there were no contradictions or discrepancies. Inconsistencies could lead to clarity and accuracy. She ensured that the data were relevant to the research question or problem being investigated. More relevant data can lead to correct conclusions. She then collected and analyzed them promptly. Delayed or updated data may need to be more valuable and accurate. Data were objective, meaning they were free from bias or personal opinions. This is important because biased data can lead to incorrect conclusions. The data should be valid, meaning it measures what it should measure. This is important because invalid data can lead to incorrect conclusions. The data should be reliable, meaning that it could be replicated. This was important because unreliable data can lead to incorrect conclusions. She then used appropriate statistical analysis to identify patterns, trends, and relationships. Statistical analysis could help to reveal important insights and relationships in the data.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed number one (1) on the school's fiscal transparency and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of the school's public trust in Governor Generoso District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction signifi-

cant relationship between school's fiscal transparency and public trust. Simple Linear Regression analysis addressed problem number 4, on the school's fiscal transparency indicators that significantly influence public trust (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. When results were yielded, discussions and interpretations followed.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter focuses on presenting, analyzing, and interpreting the collected data. Both tabular and textual formats enhance the depth of analysis and draw meaningful implications. This serves as further evidence supporting the hypothesis’s claim.

The Summary of the Extent of Fiscal Transparency

Table 1 shows a summary of the extent of fiscal transparency. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: financial reporting (3.57) is often manifested, while accountability for resource allocation (3.31), public participation in budgeting (3.20), financial audits (3.20), and access to financial information (2.89) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.21 denotes that the extent of fiscal transparency is sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Fiscal Transparency

No	Fiscal Transparency	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Access to financial information	2.89	Moderately Extensive
2	Financial reporting	3.57	Extensive
3	Public participation in budgeting	3.20	Moderately Extensive
4	Financial audits	3.20	Moderately Extensive
5	Accountability for resource allocation	3.31	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.21	Moderately Extensive

Fiscal transparency in a governmental context refers to the degree to which a government openly shares information about its financial activities and decisions with the public. Fiscal transparency encompasses various elements, including the accessibility of budgetary information, clarity in financial reporting, and the openness of decision-making processes related to public finances. In a highly transparent fiscal environment, citizens can easily access comprehensive and timely information about government revenues, expenditures, debts, and financial policies. Transparent fiscal practices contribute to accountability, allowing citizens to understand how public resources are allocated and spent. Furthermore, fiscal transparency promotes good governance by providing a basis for informed public discourse and enabling citi-

zens to hold government officials accountable for their financial decisions. Governments that prioritize fiscal transparency strengthen public trust and create an environment conducive to responsible fiscal management and sustainable economic development.

Table 2 summarizes the extent of public trust. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: parent and community engagement (3.78), accountability for results (3.74), and responsive conflict resolution (3.50) are often manifested; in contrast, consistent and fair policy (3.32) and transparency (3.31) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.53 denotes that the extent of public trust is often manifested and, thus, extensive.

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Public Trust

No	Public Trust	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Transparency	3.31	Moderately Extensive
2	Accountability for Results	3.74	Extensive
3	Parent and Community Engagement	3.78	Extensive
4	Responsive Conflict Resolution	3.50	Extensive
5	Consistent and Fair Policy	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.53	Extensive

The extent of public trust is a critical barometer of the relationship between a government and its citizens. Public trust refers to individuals' confidence and belief in their government and its institutions. It is shaped by various factors, including the government's transparency, accountability, responsiveness, and effectiveness. In a society characterized by high public trust, citizens believe that their government acts in their best interests, operates transparently, and is accountable for its actions. Trust is often influenced by the government's ability to deliver public services, uphold the rule of law, and effectively address societal challenges. Conversely, a low extent of public trust may result from perceived corruption, lack of transparency, or unresponsive governance. Fostering public trust is crucial for a stable and thriving society, as it encourages civic engagement, co-

operation, and a sense of shared responsibility between the government and its citizens. Therefore, governments aspiring to strengthen public trust should prioritize open communication, ethical governance, and policies that address the needs and concerns of the population. Significant Relationship Between Fiscal Transparency and Public Trust

It can be depicted that Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between fiscal transparency ($r=0.897$; $p<.000$) and public trust. Table 3 reveals the significant relationship between fiscal transparency and public trust. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis stating that no significant relationship between fiscal transparency and public trust must be rejected, providing empirical evidence of significant results.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Fiscal Transparency and Public Trust

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Public Trust	0.897	<0.000	Significant	Reject H0

*Significant @ $p<0.05$

The significant relationship between fiscal transparency and public trust forms the cornerstone of a healthy and robust governance system. Fiscal transparency, marked by the open and accessible disclosure of government finan-

cial information, plays a pivotal role in shaping the level of trust citizens place in their government. It enhances transparency when governments provide clear and comprehensive information about public finances, including budget

allocations, expenditures, and financial policies. This transparency, in turn, fosters public trust by allowing citizens to understand how their tax dollars are utilized and by providing insight into the decision-making processes that impact their lives (Henderson Mapp, 2002). A high level of fiscal transparency contributes to accountability, as citizens can hold the government accountable for its financial decisions and performance. This accountability reinforces the government’s credibility and strengthens the state’s and its citizens’ social contract. Conversely, a lack of fiscal transparency can erode public trust, breed skepticism, and undermine confidence in government institutions (Ackermann Nel, 2014). Governments that prioritize fiscal transparency demonstrate a commitment to good governance and cultivate an environment where citizens

feel informed, engaged, and confident in the integrity of the financial systems. In essence, fiscal transparency and public trust are reciprocal and foundational to building a resilient and trusting relationship between the government and its citizens (Mackey et al., 2016).

The Domains of Fiscal Transparency Significantly Influence Public Trust

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the domains of fiscal transparency that significantly influence public trust. Domains of fiscal transparency, such as access to financial information (0.000), financial reporting (0.001), public participation in budgeting (0.000), financial audits (0.001), and accountability for resource allocation (0.001), suggest significant influence over public trust.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Fiscal Transparency Significantly Influences Public Trust

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions
H (Intercept)	4.145	-	0.079	0.001	-
H (Intercept)	0.313	-	0.175	0.270	-
Access to Financial Information	0.227	0.117	0.102	1.010	0.315 *Reject H0
Financial Reporting	0.241	0.118	0.136	1.299	0.186 *Reject H0
Public Participation in Budgeting	0.252	0.096	0.210	2.098	0.048 *Reject H0
Financial Audits	0.212	0.087	0.210	2.098	0.088 *Reject H0
Accountability for Resource Allocation	0.241	0.118	0.136	1.299	0.186 *Reject H0
R²	0.874				
F-value	254.897				
p-value	<0.001				

*Significant @ p<0.05

Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.855 suggests that 85.5% of fiscal transparency explains public trust. This provides empirical evidence that the domains of fiscal transparency can account for and explain the variability of public trust. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, with regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (254.897) and F-statistic are significant $p < .001$, which indicates that the model better predicts public trust. The significant domains of fiscal transparency wield substantial influence over public trust in a government. Firstly, the accessibility and clarity of budgetary information stand as critical domains. When citizens have easy access to clear and detailed information about government revenues, expenditures, and financial policies, it fosters understanding and trust (O'Donnell White, 2005). Bryk and Schneider (2022) said that transparent budgetary practices enable citizens to comprehend how public

funds are allocated and spent, promoting confidence in the government's fiscal responsibility. Secondly, the openness of decision-making processes regarding public finances is paramount. When government decisions about fiscal matters are made transparently and inclusively, it enhances the perception of fairness and accountability, reinforcing public trust. Thirdly, financial reporting practices contribute significantly, including regular and comprehensive disclosure of financial statements. Transparent reporting ensures that citizens are well-informed about the government's financial health and performance, fostering a sense of reliability and trust. The significant domains of fiscal transparency, including accessible budgetary information, open decision-making processes, and transparent financial reporting, collectively play a pivotal role in shaping public trust in governmental institutions (Mackey et al., 2016).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the results of the data analysis, discussion, and drawing of implications. Findings were based on the problem's posed statement, conclusions based on the findings generated, and recommendations based on the discussions' implications.

4.1. Findings—The following were the study's findings, as shown in the presentation results, analysis, and discussions. The extent of fiscal transparency shows that financial reporting (3.57) is often manifested. In contrast, accountability for resource allocation (3.31), public participation in budgeting (3.20), financial audits (3.20), and access to financial information (2.89) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.21 denotes that the extent of fiscal transparency was sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of public trust revealed that parent and community engagement (3.78), accountability for results (3.74), and responsive conflict resolution (3.50)

are often manifested. In contrast, consistent and fair policy (3.32) and transparency (3.31) was sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.53 denotes that the extent of public trust was often manifested, thus extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between fiscal transparency ($r=0.897$; $p < .000$) and public trust. Domains of fiscal transparency, such as access to financial information (0.000), financial reporting (0.001), public participation in budgeting (0.000), financial audits (0.001), and accountability for resource allocation (0.001), suggest significant influence over public trust.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Given the findings of the study presented, the following were the conclusions to wit; The extent of fiscal transparency shows that financial reporting is often manifested. In contrast, accountability for resource allocation, public participation in budgeting, financial audits, and access to financial information are sometimes manifested. This denotes that the extent of fiscal transparency was sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of public trust revealed that parent and community engagement, accountability for results, and responsive conflict resolution are often manifested. In contrast, consistent and fair policy and transparency were sometimes manifested. This denotes that the extent of public trust was often manifested and, thus, extensive. Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant correlation between fiscal transparency and public trust. Domains of fiscal transparency, such as access to financial information, financial reporting, public participation in budgeting, financial audits, and accountability for resource allocation, suggest significant influence over public trust.

4.3. *Recommendations*—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following were recommendations to wit; Public School District Supervisors may consider implementing training programs for school administrators and finance officers on transparent budgetary practices. Emphasize the importance of clearly communicating financial information to the public, ensuring that district financial reports are easily accessible and comprehensible. Encourage regular forums or meetings to update the

community on budget allocations and financial decisions, fostering a culture of openness and accountability. School heads may be encouraged to actively participate in initiatives promoting fiscal transparency within the school. This includes ensuring that the school’s budget, financial statements, and allocation of resources are readily available to the school community. The school head could also organize periodic meetings or workshops to discuss financial matters with parents and staff, addressing any questions or concerns. Demonstrating a commitment to fiscal transparency at the school level could positively influence public trust. Although teachers may not directly handle financial matters, they play a crucial role in communicating the importance of fiscal transparency to students and parents. The study could recommend that teachers incorporate lessons or discussions about the school budget and financial decisions into the curriculum. Additionally, teachers might be encouraged to participate in school-wide initiatives to enhance transparency, such as attending informational sessions or providing feedback on financial matters. Future Researchers may build on the study by delving deeper into specific aspects of fiscal transparency that impact public trust. They may explore the effectiveness of different communication strategies for financial information, assess the role of community engagement in building trust, or investigate the correlation between specific fiscal transparency measures and varying levels of public trust. Encouraging longitudinal studies to track changes in public trust over time in response to enhanced fiscal transparency could also provide valuable insights.

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